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Research Article

**DETERMINING THE OCCURRENCE OF DEPRESSIVE
SYMPTOMS AND ANXIETY TO EVALUATE MENTAL
HEALTH AMONG THE MEDICAL STUDENTS OF
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Abstract:

Objective: To decide the recurrence of anxiety side effects and uneasiness among the clinical graduates of Pakistan to assess emotional wellness among them.

Methods: An example size of 250 clinical understudies was remembered for the study. Questionnaire were flowed and sick by understudies of first, second, third, fourth and last year MBBS. DMS IV models was utilized to gauge the degree of despondency and tension among the understudies. Our current research was conducted at Lahore Medical College, Lahore Pakistan, from September 2018 to March 2019, six months in the wake of achieving authorization from the school. The chi-square test was applied with a 5% level of criticalness to decide related variables for tension and misery individually.

Results: Anxiety was available in 160 (64%) understudies and sadness in 90 (36%) students. With female preponderance. Age ($p=0.014$), sex ($p=0.015$), ordinary examinational methods ($p=0.001$) and distressing test plan ($p=0.001$) were altogether connected with misery.

Conclusion: One fourth of understudies were found to have tension and melancholy which was related with sexual orientation and expanding age.

keywords: Anxiety, depression, DMS IV criteria.

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INTRODUCTION:

medical students preferably the ungraduated have been seen to face sheer stressful situations during their medical programmers' study done in Egypt estimated that the prevalence of the disorder was 1096% in different ethnic groups studying nationwide in medical schools. Along with many internal factors that serves to be a cause of the stress, anxiety and depressive state of the students there have been many external factors reported to have added on to this state [1]. These factors are extreme pressure being laid down by the universities in the form of extensive syllabus and lack of relaxational facilities, irregular lengthy teaching hours, peer pressure, extensive examinations, expectations of the family, financial constraints, repeated failure owing to difficult curriculum and stressful work environment. Apart from these external factors age of the student with decreasing mental capability to handle anxiety, gender; female being more prone to develop such disorders fairly quickly as compared to male counterparts, Type A personality and social upbringing plays a pivotal role in early development and appearance of the signs and symptoms of depression and anxiety and indulgence in drug abuse ,smoking and drinking. Only two such studies have been conducted in UAE.a few in Egypt and Pakistan [2].

The Basic objective of the study is to evaluate the frequency and prevalence of depressive disorder and anxiety among medical students to help them reduce the risk of associated morbidities, improve life quality and mental health. There had been a rapid rise in percentages of anxiety and depression among people in general. Anxiety tops the list of major concerns of the students followed by depression and family affairs. During anxious states our body responds by generating a flight and flight response that leads to activation of sympathetic nervous system that brings about a series of responses that prepare the body to endure stress [3]. However, exposing oneself to this response for long stretch of time leads to catastrophic effects of the wellbeing of the body. The pituitary gland releases adrenocorticotrophic hormone which serves as a major stress hormone and leads to the release of cortisol from adrenal gland. Cortisol is a corticosteroid that has many defensive purposes in the body.apar from the pituitary adrenal axis another system is the activation of sympathetic nervous system that causes the release of epinephrine and nor epinephrine hormone from the adrenal gland (medulla).They primarily increase the heart rate, respiratory rate and increases the blood pressure to optimize the working capacity of the body. The human body respond to anxiety and stress in graded fashion, ranging from stage of denial, stage of

action,stage of fatigue to stage of adaptation. Failure of this graded response at any stage leads to development of mental disorder such as depression and chronic anxiety and permanent liability to the nervous system that has serious effects in long run [4].

METHOD AND MATERIAL:

it is a cross-sectional study that was conducted between September 2018 and march 2019 at Lahore medical college. A questionnaire was circulted and filled by randomly selected medical students of all the years in MBBS. a sample size of 250 students was used calculates using WHO sample size calculator. Data was fed into spss version 19.0 and analyzed using 95% confidence interval. Frequency and prevalence was calculated. And presented in the form of tables. The prevalence of stress was compared in both genders and different age groups. Statistics as percentages, frequencies and chi-square test was used to sum up the results. The 95% confidence intervals were calculated and a p value of less than .005 was taken to be significant.

RESULT:

The result consisted of 250 students out of which 160(64%) were suffering from anxiety and 90 students (36%) were suffering from clinically evident Depression with female preponderance($p=0.014$).212 students (85%) were females and only 90 students (15%) were males. Average age of the students ranged from 21 to 25 years old. Cause of Anxiety for 53% was tough examination schedule ($p=0.001$) while for 49 % it was examination techniques ($p=0.001$) .students of final year mostly regarded aniyty and depression to be a state self-created by the body in response to a stressful stimulus.about 62% of the students reported to have been experiencing palpitations, panic states, loss of appetite, loss of pleasure and interest, emotional instability and disturbed sleep pattern. 24% of the students have anxiety spells once a week,36% had reported it to be 2 to 3 times a week and rest of them had been continuously facing stressful states leading to clinically underdiagnosed depression.

DISCUSSION:

Most of the young adulthood is exposed to challenging na d changing environment that results in axiety and stress which if remained persistent results in Chronic depression. Most of this time is spent and colleges and universities which in our sample population is the medical school. Most of the students also come from low socioeconomic backgrounds with financial constraints and liabilities Outgrowing their mental capabilities and demotivating them in the long run. Emotional attachments and failure to cope up with their commitment aggravates their anxiety. Anxiety and

depression is a very common occurrence among medical students globally. A number of studies confirm the dramatic decrease in cognitive capabilities, ability to tackle problematic situations and mental and emotional burnouts that may even lead to suicidal ideations and morbidities as metabolic syndrome has been directly associated with them [5]. Majority of these cases go unnoticed while some student start self-medications as well while other resort to drug and substance abuse. These mental states are mostly apparent in students of third, fourth and final year. Being in depression weakens their immune systems and leads to more susceptibility to infectious diseases and allergic reactions. Higher levels of anxiety and depression are found in females owing to many psychological and social pressures [6].

However, some studies do not support any association with gender among masses. Students usually report medical conditions such as headache, myalgias, lower backaches, lack of concentration and focus secondary to chronic anxiety and depression. Later on which can manifest as serious complications of stroke, cardiovascular events, early onset of diabetes, metabolic syndrome, gastric ulcers, hypertension and even cancers [7]. About 60% of the students admitted to have had suicidal ideations somewhere in their medical school tenure [8]. Many resort to social isolations and phobia development Anxiety and depression is turning out to be a major health concern for the young doctors leading to early demise and causalities. A study done in India reported positive association between low level of physical activity due to long study hours and early onset of depression while other study reports it higher in students with lower BMI.

CONCLUSION:

There is prevalence of depression and anxiety among medical students with positive significant

association with age and gender having more female preponderance.

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